

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON THE CONTENT OF FLAVONOIDS IN THE EXTRACTS OF *RUMEX PATIENTIA* L. × *RUMEX TIANSHANICUS* LOSINSKY HERB

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Abstract

The search and study of new promising plants and the development of medicines based on them are relevant for modern pharmacy.

*The aim of the research was to determine the quantitative content of total flavonoids in extracts from *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb and to investigate the influence of pharmaceutical factors on the degree of their extraction.*

***Materials and methods.** The objects of the study were extracts obtained from the aerial part of sorrel, harvested during the flowering period in 2023 at the experimental plots of the Department of Cultural Flora of the M. M. Hryshko National Botanical Garden of the NAS of Ukraine. The quantitative content of total flavonoids was determined by spectrophotometric method.*

***Results and discussion.** The total flavonoids content in series 5 obtained by maceration with stirring was the highest compared to other series and amounted to 2.98 mg/ml. In series 9, the total flavonoids content was the highest compared to other series obtained by remaceration, amounting to 3.23 mg/ml. The total flavonoids content in series 13 was the highest compared to other series obtained by maceration with forced extractant flow and amounted to 3.57 mg/ml.*

***Conclusion.** The content of total flavonoids in extracts from *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb obtained by different methods has been determined. It has been found that the highest amount of flavonoids (3.57 mg/ml), expressed as rutin equivalent, is extracted from the series 13 obtained using 70% ethanol as the extractant, the extraction method of maceration with forced extractant flow, and at the ratio of raw material to extractant of 1:5.*

Keywords: *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky, herb, flavonoids, extraction method.

INTRODUCTION

The search and study of new promising plants and the development of medicines based on them are relevant for modern pharmacy [1, 2]. Medicinal products based on plant raw materials are widely used in traditional medicine of many countries. After conducting an analysis of the domestic pharmaceutical market, it was established that in Ukraine there are no medicines based on raw materials of *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsk – a hybrid that was selectively obtained by crossing spinach sorrel (*Rumex patientia*) and Tianshan sorrel (*Rumex tianschanicus*). This plant is also known as “Uteusha spinach” and was bred to grow affordable animal feed. But sorrel has found application in the food, energy and medical fields [3, 4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The objects of the study were extracts obtained from the aerial part of sorrel, harvested during the flowering period in 2023 at the experimental plots of the Department of Cultural Flora of the M. M. Hryshko National Botanical Garden of the NAS of Ukraine (Kyiv).

The quantitative content of total flavonoids was determined by spectrophotometric method, recalculated as rutin, using a LabAnalyt SP-V1000 spectrophotometer.

Quantitative determination of flavonoids content.

Test solution. Aliquot of the obtained alcohol extract is placed into a 25 ml volumetric flask, added 10 ml of alcohol (70% (vol/vol)), 2.0 ml of 3% alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) solution of aluminum chloride, added alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) to the mark and it is mixed.

Compensatory solution. Aliquot of the obtained alcohol extract is placed into a 25 ml volumetric flask and added alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) to the mark and it is mixed.

Standard sample solution of rutin. 0.05 g (exact weight) of the standard sample of rutin is placed in a 100 ml volumetric flask, then 70 ml of alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) are added, dissolved and added alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) to the mark and stirred.

Comparison solution. 1.0 ml of the standard sample solution of rutin is placed in a 25 ml volumetric flask, added 2.0 ml of 3% alcohol (70% (vol/vol))

aluminum chloride solution, and added alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) to the mark and stirred.

Compensatory solution. 1.0 ml of the standard sample solution of rutin is placed in a 25 ml volumetric flask and added alcohol (70% (vol/vol)) to the mark and stirred.

The optical density of the test solution and the comparison solution are measured 45 min after preparation at wavelength 408 nm relatively to the compensatory solutions for each one respectively.

The total flavonoids content was calculated in terms of rutin, in mg/100 ml [5, 6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to obtain extraction-based medicines, it is necessary to select the extraction method, the type of

extractant, and the ratio of raw materials to extractant, which are factors influencing the extraction process. Therefore, to study all the investigated technological parameters, the method of experimental design was used, which allowed reducing the total number of experiments (Table).

For the experiment planning, one of the dispersion analysis plans was used – a third-order Latin square. This allowed for the implementation of only 16 experimental series and obtaining the necessary information about the influence of the type of extractant, extraction method, and the ratio of raw material to extractant on the extraction process of total flavonoids [5].

Table

List of technological factors studied during extraction of *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky.

Factor	Level of factor
A – the type of extractant	a ₁ – 20% ethanol a ₂ – 40% ethanol a ₃ – 50% ethanol a ₄ – 70% ethanol
B – the ratio of raw materials to extractant	b ₁ – 1 : 5 b ₂ – 1 : 8 b ₃ – 1 : 10 b ₄ – 1 : 12
C – extraction method	c ₁ – maceration c ₂ – maceration with stirring c ₃ – remaceration c ₄ – maceration with forced extractant flow

The extraction process involved the following steps: the aerial part of *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb was ground and soaked in various ratios (1:5, 1:8, 1:10, 1:12) of extractant (20%, 40%, 50%, and 70% ethanol) according to the experimental design matrix.

For the extraction of biological active substance from the sorrel herb, the following methods were used:

- Maceration
- Remaceration
- Maceration with forced extractant flow
- Maceration with stirring

During maceration with stirring, the *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb was immersed in the extractant and allowed to steep for seven days with periodic mixing. The resulting extracts were drained, and the residue was rinsed with the extractant. Subsequently, the obtained extracts were combined and filtered using a paper filter.

The difference between maceration and maceration with stirring lies in the periodic mixing of *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb with the extractant.

During remaceration, the *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb was immersed in

the extractant, which was previously divided into three equal portions. Each portion was steeped with the sorrel herb for one day. The drained extracts were combined, and *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky residue was rinsed with the extractant. Subsequently, the obtained extracts were combined and filtered through a pleated paper filter [5].

Using the extraction method known as maceration with forced extractant flow, the *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb was subjected to pressure from the extractant for a day. The resulting extract was drained, and then the herb was soaked in it again. This process was repeated for three days. Subsequently, the *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky residue was rinsed with the extractant. The obtained extracts were combined and filtered using a paper filter.

After evaluating the influence of the nature of the extractant, the ratio of raw material to extractant, and the extraction method on the extraction of flavonoids from the *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb, the results obtained were presented in the figures 1-3.

The results of the quantitative determination of total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by maceration with stirring are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by maceration with stirring

The total flavonoids content in series 5 was the highest compared to other series obtained by maceration with stirring and amounted to 2.98 mg/ml. A slightly lower amount of flavonoids was determined in series 15, which was 2.85 mg/ml. The lowest flavonoids content was found in series 2 (0.99 mg/ml).

The results of the quantitative determination of total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by remaceration are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by remaceration

The total flavonoids content in series 9 was the highest compared to other series obtained by remaceration and amounted to 3.23 mg/ml. A slightly lower amount of flavonoids was determined in series 14, which was 3.13 mg/ml. The flavonoid content in series 4 was 0.51 mg/ml, which is 6.4 times less compared to the content in series 9.

The results of the quantitative determination of total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by maceration with forced extractant flow are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Total flavonoids content in extracts obtained by maceration with forced extractant flow

The total flavonoids content in series 13 was the highest compared to other series obtained by maceration with forced extractant flow and amounted to 3.57 mg/ml. A slightly lower amount of flavonoids was determined in series 10, which was 3.02 mg/ml. The flavonoids content in series 3 was 0.77 mg/ml, which is 4.6 times less compared to the content in series 13.

CONCLUSION.

Based on the analysis of literature sources, it has been established that sorrel herb is a valuable source of many biologically active substances, including flavonoids.

The content of total flavonoids in extracts from *Rumex patientia* L. × *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsky herb obtained by different methods has been determined. It has been found that the highest amount of flavonoids (3.57 mg/ml), expressed as rutin equivalent, is extracted from the series 13 obtained using 70% ethanol as the extractant, the extraction method of maceration with forced extractant flow, and at the ratio of raw material to extractant of 1:5.

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